

1 **Development of innovative antioxidant food packaging systems**
2 **based on natural extracts from food industry waste and Moringa**
3 **oleifera leaves**

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19
20 **Abstract**

21 Active packaging that prolongs food shelf-life, maintaining its quality and safety, is an increasing
22 industrial demand, especially if integrated in a circular economy model. This study focused on the
23 fabrication and characterization of sustainable cellulose-based active packaging using food-industry
24 waste and natural extracts as antioxidant agents. Grape marc, olive pomace and moringa leaves
25 extracts obtained by supercritical fluid, antisolvent and maceration extraction in different solvents
26 were compared for their antioxidant power and phenolic content. Grape and moringa macerates in
27 acetone and methanol, as most efficient and cost-effective extracts, were incorporated in the

28 packaging as coatings or in-between layers. Both systems showed significant free-radicals protection
29 *in vitro* (antioxidant power ~50%) and more than 50% lipid peroxidation prevention of ground beef
30 over 16 days by indirect TBARS and direct *in situ* Raman microspectroscopy measurements.
31 Therefore, they retained to be promising for industrial application and for more sustainable farm-to-
32 fork food production systems.

33

34 *Keywords: Active packaging, natural antioxidants, cellulose biopolymer, meat shelf-life, food waste*
35 *recovery, radicals scavenging*

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Food safety represents a global priority and one of the major concerns of consumers, administration,
39 and industry. The goal of food packaging is to satisfy customers and industry requirements containing
40 the food in a cost-effective and appealing way, while maintaining intact the food safety and quality
41 minimizing the environmental impact (Marsh & Bugusu, 2007).

42 The demand of sustainable active packaging systems is increasing together with the compelling need
43 of safe ready-to-eat and long-life products. Within this frame, the development of innovative food
44 packaging materials represents a challenge of main interest in the food-research field.

45 Nowadays, biopolymers are considered as the best candidates to substitute non-biodegradable and
46 non-renewable packaging materials thanks to their environmentally friendly characteristics (Rhim et
47 al., 2013). All natural biopolymers, such as cellulose or starch derivatives, are biodegradable under
48 open atmospheric conditions for definition (Karak, 2012).

49 However, these days environment protection remains one of the greatest issues that food industry has
50 to face, including the management of huge amounts of waste. For instance, during the production of
51 wine and olive oil, from 10 to 20% of the total weight of plants material is discarded, leading to the
52 necessity of managing millions of tons of dregs per year (Lafka et al., 2007). Most of the antioxidant
53 active compounds such as phenolic molecules or flavonoids remain in the discarded part of the plant
54 such as skins, seeds and leaves (Rodis et al., 2002). Thus, the employment of this kind of food-related
55 industry waste as natural active compounds in biopolymeric food packaging material has generated
56 a great interest in the last few years in a context of circular economy and pollution sources reduction.
57 This follows the European Green Deal purpose to halve the global food waste production per capita
58 by 2030, ensuring an efficient and sustainable use of natural resources and of moving towards more
59 healthy and sustainable food systems (EU Green Deal Cluster 6 Food).

60 In addition, natural plant derivatives can be considered as a safer and cost-effective alternative to
61 synthetic antioxidant agents (Barbosa-Pereira et al., 2014; Realini & Marcos, 2014).

62 Many studies have already focused their attention on the development of active films containing
63 natural antioxidants, efficient to enhance the myoglobin stability and fresh meat preservation from
64 oxidation (C. Nerín et al., 2008; Cristina Nerín et al., 2006). The natural antioxidant agents can be
65 incorporated directly in the meat package as scavenger of free radicals or as autoxidation protectors
66 (Moudache et al., 2016). The main advantage is that the agent does not need to be added to food, in
67 compliance with European legislation (Regulation (EC) No. 1333/2008).

68 The presence of carboxylic groups on the conjugated ring structures of many compounds contained
69 in plants derivatives allow to neutralize free radicals or decompose peroxides (Adedapo et al., 2008)
70 leading to the inhibition of lipid peroxidation (Oyedemi et al., 2012), which is one of the main causes

71 of food degradation during its processing and storage. It involves a chain reaction process driven by
72 the formation of secondary products and free radicals that enhance the lipid auto-oxidation while
73 negatively influencing the overall quality of foods, including flavor, taste, nutritional values, and
74 promoting the production of toxic compounds. Thus, the shelf-life prolongation of fresh foods
75 containing fatty acids, such as meat or fish, is strictly bounded to a reduction or a slowdown of these
76 reactions.

77 However, the real effectiveness of the natural antioxidants in the finished active packaging depends
78 on many aspects such as i) the extraction method, which can influence the final content of active
79 compounds, ii) the kind of polymer which might change its physical, mechanical, optical and barrier
80 properties upon the incorporation of active agents, iii) the chemical interaction of the active
81 compounds within the film which may affect their antioxidant efficacy. Thus, the design of active
82 food packaging polymers with natural extracts able to exploit their efficacy in each stage of
83 production, from the extraction to their application on real food, while maintaining economic and
84 environmental sustainability remains very challenging and must be deeply investigated.

85 The objective of the present study was to develop and characterize sustainable active food packaging
86 employing industrial food processing waste and natural extracts as antioxidant agents to preserve
87 foods from the oxidative damage remaining in a context of circular economy and pollution sources
88 reduction. The analysis of the antioxidant properties of the active agents proposed here was performed
89 at each crucial step of the active films production from the extraction of the active compounds to their
90 application on real food matrices by many different and complementary techniques offering an
91 evaluation of their efficacy as comprehensive as possible.

92 **2. Material and Methods**

93 *2.1 Chemicals*

94 DPPH powder, gallic acid (GA, 97.5-102.5%), 2,20-azobis(2methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride
95 (AAPH, 97%), fluorescein (3,60-dihydroxy-9H-xanthen-2-one); 6-
96 hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (Trolox, 98%); potassium phosphate dibasic
97 heptahydrate, potassium phosphate monobasic di-hydrate, Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent, sodium
98 salicylate (>99.5%), 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (>99%), hydrogen peroxide (>50%), and
99 malondialdehyde tetrabutylammonium salt (MDA, >96%) were from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy).

100 Methanol (HPLC grade), ethanol absolute anhydrous, acetone, glacial acetic acid (>99%), sodium
101 carbonate, trichloroacetic acid (TCA, >99%) and paraffin oil were from Carlo Erba (Cornaredo, MI,
102 Italy). Orthophosphoric acid (85%, reagent grade) and sodium hydroxide (0.01 mol/l) were from
103 Scharlab (Barcelona, Spain). 4,6-dihydroxy-2-mercaptopyrimidine (2-thiobarbituric acid, TBA,
104 98%) was from Acros Organics (Rodano, Milan, Italy).

105 For bacterial cultivation and assays, Muller Hilton (MH) broth and agar purchased from Lickson
106 (Palermo, Italy), phosphate buffer saline (PBS) tablets for 200 ml from PanReac AppliChem
107 (Barcelona, Spain) and sodium chloride by Carlo Erba were used.

108 Standard polyphenols and reagents used for the UPLC-TQ-MS analysis: caffeine (CAS 58-08-2)
109 [CAF], (+)catechin (>99.0%, 154-23-4) [C], (-)epicatechin (>95%, 490-46-0) [EC], (-)epicatechin
110 gallate (>98%, 1257-08-5) [ECG], (-)catechin gallate (>98% 130405-40-2) [CG],
111 (-)epigallocatechin (>95% 970-74-1) [EGC], (-)gallocatechin (>98% 3371-27-5) [GC],
112 (-)gallocatechin gallate (>98%, 4233-96-9) [GCG] and (-)epigallocatechin gallate (>95%, 989-51-
113 5) [ECG], all from Sigma Aldrich. Formic acid was from Waters (Manchester, UK). Ultrapure water

114 was obtained from a Wasserlab Ultramatic GR system (Barbatáin, Spain).

115 **2.2 Analysis of the plant extracts**

116 *2.2.1 Plant materials and extractive methods*

117 Moringa desiccated leaves (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) were purchased from Alesframa (Málaga, Spain).

118 The olive pomace (*Olea europaea* fruits harvested in December 2020) was supplied by a local olive
119 oil mill in Ayerbe (Spain, 42° 18 '12' N, 1° 57' 53' W). Grape marc (skin and seeds) obtained from
120 the “Garnacha” variety for red wine production was collected after the pressing of the fruits harvested
121 in the zone of Rioja Baja, near Calahorra (Spain, 42° 16 '36' N, 0° 41 '21' W) in October 2020.

122 The three plant materials were extracted in University of Zaragoza (Spain) by three techniques:

123 i) Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) using CO₂ in three steps. The solid residues were collected
124 manually from each of the two collectors. Then, hexane was employed to dissolve and collect the
125 remaining residues in another two fractions.

126 ii) A part of the solid residues collected from SFE extractor were macerated in ethanol to solubilize
127 them and processed in a second extractor to perform supercritical antisolvent extraction (SAE)
128 employing CO₂ in two steps. Firstly, from the extractor two fractions were collected, one manually
129 and another after its dissolution in ethanol. Then, the remaining residues after another step of pressure
130 regulation were collected manually from the collector. The scheme of the extractions and the collected
131 fractions is presented in Supplementary Information (SI) (Figure S1).

132 All the extracts fractions were solubilized in ethanol, or water and ethanol 1:1 at a final concentration
133 of 1400 ± 5 mg/l for moringa and grape extracts, and of 5000 ± 13 mg/l for the olive cake extracts.

134 iii) Maceration (MAC) was applied at room temperature (25 °C) to plant residues and leaves by using
135 methanol, ethanol, acetone and DCM (100 g of plant sample per liter of solvent). Cold and hot water
136 was also considered. Samples were kept at dark for 10 and 30 days, in closed glass bottles and they
137 were shaken every two days. After maceration, samples were filtered (Whatman qualitative filter
138 paper grade 1), concentrated in a rotary evaporator Büchi R-124 (Flawil, Switzerland) until about 5
139 ml, and finally air-dried in glass Petri dishes for 48 h.

140 All solutions were placed in glass tubes, stirred and sonicated for at least 1 h at 300 W (Q-Sonica
141 Q700 sonicator, 20 kHz, Newtown, CT, USA). Then the tubes were covered with aluminium foil,
142 plugged and sealed with Parafilm® M and stored at 4 °C until their analysis.

143 A legend of all the fractions analysed is reported in SI (Table S1).

144 *2.2.2 Determination of the total phenols content by Folin-Ciocalteu assay*

145 The protocol was adapted by the official method described by Kupina et al. (Kupina et al., 2018).
146 Briefly, five dilutions of gallic acid (40 mg/l - 200 mg/l) were obtained in Milli-Q® water to build
147 the standard calibration curve. A series of test tubes, each containing 3 ml of water, 200 µl of Folin-
148 Ciocalteu reagent were prepared and in each tube was added one of the following: 200 µl of sample
149 test solution; calibration standard solution or water as blank. They were vortexed and allowed to settle
150 for 6 min.

151 Then, 200 µl of a 20% (w/v) sodium carbonate solution was added to each tube and mixed well. All
152 the test tubes were incubated at 37 ± 1 °C for 30 min and then 200 µl of each sample were placed in
153 a well of a 96-well plate in triplicate. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm in a multiwell reader,
154 by subtracting the absorbance of the blank. A linear fit was calculated from the gallic acid calibration
155 curve and the total phenolic content % (w/w) of each sample was calculated interpolating their

156 average absorbance subtracted of the blank from the fit, normalizing the results by the concentration
157 of the sample (mg/l).

158 2.2.3 UPLC-TQ-MS analysis of polyphenols

159 UPLC-TQ-MS is a sensitive and reliable technique already used for the determination of polyphenols
160 in plants, such as mint (Krzyzanowska et al., 2011) or sweet tea tree (Ning et al., 2019). All the plant
161 extracts solubilized in ethanol were analyzed by UPLC-TQ-MS targeted for polyphenolic compounds
162 using the standards listed in the chemicals. Semi-quantitative analysis was carried out injecting 10 µl
163 of each sample in an Acquity™ UPLC coupled to an electrospray ionization (ESI) interface used in
164 both positive and negative mode with a capillary voltage of 3.5 kV and Xevo TQ-S microdetector
165 (Waters, Manchester, UK). A UPLC BEH C18 column of 1.7 µm particle size (2.1 × 100 mm) was
166 used at a flow rate of 0.3 ml/min at 35 °C. The mobile phases were water (phase A) and methanol
167 (phase B), both with 0.1% formic acid. Gradient 95% A /5% B (6 min); 5%A /95% B (10 min). The
168 sampling cone voltage was optimized for each compound by using standards, and it was set at 40 V.
169 The source and desolvation gas (400 l/h) temperatures were 150 and 350 °C, respectively. Selected
170 Ion Recording (SIR) mode was used. MassLynx v.4.1 software was used for data acquisition and
171 processing. Analyses were performed in duplicate. For each phenolic compound, the result was
172 expressed as normalized areas by dividing its area by the sum of the areas of all compounds of interest
173 and multiplying by 100. For instance, in the case of GA:

$$174 A_{GA}\% = A_{GA} / [A_{GA} + A_{CAF} + A_{EC} + A_{CG} + A_{ECG} + A_{GC} + A_{EGC} + A_{GCG} + A_{EGCG}] \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

175 2.2.4 Antibacterial activity evaluation

176 *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 75380 were used for this work as a
177 Gram – and a Gram + bacterial model, respectively. The assay performed in this work is described in
178 SI.

179 2.2.5 Antioxidant activity evaluation

180 2.2.5.1 DPPH radical scavenging activity

181 The reduction of the 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical signal at 516 nm was measured
182 using a multiplate reader Varioskan LUX (Thermo Scientific, Rodano, Milan, Italy) following the
183 method previously described by Prieto (Prieto, 2012). Details can be found in SI. The radical
184 scavenging activity or the antioxidant power (AP%) after one hour of incubation with the DPPH for
185 each extract was expressed as the percentage of reduction of the free radical by the sample and
186 calculated as follows:

$$187 \text{ AP\%} = [(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}})/A_{\text{control}}] \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

188 where A_{control} is the mean of the methanolic DPPH controls (DPPH in methanol) absorbance values
189 subtracted of methanol absorbance, and A_{sample} is the mean of each samples replicates absorbance
190 values (DPPH with extracts) subtracted of their methanolic blank absorbance values (extracts in
191 methanol). The AP% of GA at 8 different concentrations from 0.06 mg/l to 2.5 mg/l was measured
192 as well as internal control. The extracts that did not reached almost the 50% of AP% were excluded
193 from further analysis. For each sample, five concentrations (AP% between 20% and 70%) were
194 chosen and a linear fit was calculated. The half maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) was calculated
195 from the linear range of each sample.

196 *2.2.5.2 ORAC assay*

197 Working solutions were prepared following the Association of Official Agricultural Chemists
198 (AOAC) standard method described by Ou et al. (Ou et al., 2013). Details can be found in SI. The net
199 area under curve (AUC) was calculated for each sample including the Trolox dilutions by summation
200 of all the fluorescence measurements over time, normalized by their initial fluorescence values. Then
201 the Trolox calibration curve was obtained by plotting the calculated net AUC over Trolox tested
202 moieties (μmol). Each sample average AUC was interpolated in the calculated linear fit to obtain
203 μmol of relative Trolox equivalents (TE). The ORAC values were calculated as μmol of TE per gram
204 of sample.

205 *2.2.5.3 Uncertainty budget evaluation*

206 For both DPPH and ORAC results, the relative uncertainty budget was calculated for each value
207 considering, linear fit, all the uncertainties related both to the x-axis and to the y-axis. For the first,
208 the sample pureness, each dilution performed (considering for the final volume uncertainty the
209 propagation of the ones related to each specific pipette used) and the weighing of the sample, were
210 considered. For the second, a propagation of the calculated standard uncertainty values, derived from
211 the three replicates of absorbance (DPPH) or AUC measurements (ORAC), was performed.

212 *2.3 Active films production*

213 The developed film was composed of 45 μm -thickness cellulose-based biopolymer NatureFlex™ NK
214 by Futamura UK Ltd (Burgos, Spain). The optimum conditions corresponded to 5% (w/w) of the
215 moringa leaves and olive extracts, which were mixed in a safe food-contact varnish methyl ethyl
216 ketone-based, ADCOTE™ 17-3, by DOW Chemical Ibérica (Madrid, Spain). They were manually

217 coated as a homogeneous layer on the cellulose biopolymer employing a wire close wound bar (bar
218 number: 7; color code: brown; wire diameter: 1.02 mm; wet film deposit: 80 μm). Samples with 5%
219 (w/w) of GA and with varnish were prepared as well as positive control and blank respectively (SI
220 Figure S2).

221 The grape marc macerates were included at the same concentration of the other sample in a water-
222 based biodegradable adhesive (Flex Tack 4M35) for food packaging applications from Samtack
223 (Barcelona, Spain). The active adhesive was spread on the cellulose sheet using the coating machine
224 K control coater from RK print coat instruments (Litlington, UK) using the same bar. The cellulose
225 sheet with dry adhesive was covered by another cellulose layer. The developed double-layer
226 biomaterial was placed in BiO 330 A3 Heavy Duty Laminator (South Korea), and it was pressed at
227 40 °C with a speed number 5. A positive and negative control with 5% of Trolox and with pure
228 adhesive, respectively, were prepared as well.

229 ***2.4 Characterization of antioxidant activity***

230 *2.4.1 DPPH radical scavenging activity of active films*

231 The DPPH inhibition assay applied directly on active films was already previously described
232 (Benbettaïeb et al., 2018; Busolo & Lagaron, 2015). Briefly, squares of 2 \times 2 cm were cut in triplicate
233 from each active film including the controls. They were put in sterile Falcon tubes and covered with
234 aluminum foils, and then 12 ml of DPPH radical solution (50 mg/l) were put in each one including
235 one without any film as control. Aliquots of 200 μl of each replicate of each sample were collected
236 immediately after the addition of the DPPH and after 24 h, and their absorbance at 516 nm was
237 measured. Then the AP% was calculated for all the samples including the blank at the two time points.

238 *2.4.2 Free radical scavenging assay of active films*

239 Antioxidant capacity of all cellulose-based active films was measured using a method developed by
240 Pezo et al. (Pezo et al., 2006) (SI Figure S3).

241 The method consists of the hydroxylation of salicylic acid, to 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (2,5-DHB),
242 by the free OH· radicals generated from an aqueous H₂O₂ aerosol, under UV-light irradiation.
243 Samples of 1 dm² of each active cellulose films were placed inside PE bags of 150 × 150 mm. An
244 impulse sealer PFS-200 Zhejiang Dongfeng Packing Machine Co (Wenzhou, Zhejiang, China) was
245 used to thermo-seal the bags that were placed in triplicate in a holder and connected to the OH· radical
246 generator. The assessment of oxidation of the samples has been carried out for 24 h. As a result, the
247 percentage of hydroxylation (H%) has been obtained according to the formula where 100% is the
248 peak area of 2,5-DHB in the blank sample (control) and x% is the area of the 2,5-DHB peak in a
249 sample with antioxidants.

250
$$H\% = [\text{Area}_{2,5\text{DHB (active film)}} / \text{Area}_{2,5\text{DHB (blank)}}] \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

251 *2.4.3 TBARS assay to assess lipid oxidation reduction in ground beef*

252 12 g of fresh beef meat, from a local butchery, minced twice with a content of about 50% of fat were
253 weighted for each of the tested film samples and packaged individually in two film squares of 6 × 6
254 cm over and above the meat piece, flattening it to make sure that all the active area was in full contact
255 with meat.

256 Each sample was inserted in a PET thermo-saleable bag of 12 cm × 14 cm and sealed aerobically
257 with non-modified atmosphere air and stored in the fridge at 4 °C. Samples were prepared in triplicate
258 for each kind of film, including the blank, and for each time of analysis (0, 3, 6, 9 and 16 days), to

259 follow the meat lipid peroxidation over time. The thiobarbituric acid index (TBARS value) was
260 determined by adapting previously described protocols (Ahn et al., 1998; Henriott et al., 2020; Nerín,
261 2010; Ribeiro et al., 2021) (details in SI). The concentration of MDA in the samples was calculated
262 interpolating the values in the linear fit obtained from the calibration curve. TBARS values were
263 expressed as mg of MDA per kg of meat. All measurements were made in triplicate. The statistical
264 significance of the difference between the average of the measurements on the blank and the active
265 samples was analyzed performing a t-test and the relative p-value were calculated.

266 *2.4.4 Raman evaluation of meat oxidation*

267 Just before the TBARS assay, each meat sample was analyzed by Raman spectroscopy immediately
268 after opening the packaging and flattening the meat as much as possible. Before data collection, the
269 alignment and calibration of the Raman DXR™ Thermo Fisher Scientific microscope was performed
270 using the instrument calibration tool. A 10× dry objective (0.25 NA) with a 50 μm slit confocal
271 aperture was employed. The analyzed spectral range was 3500–200 cm⁻¹. All the spectra were
272 acquired using an excitation wavelength of 780 nm with a power of 5.0 mW, exposure time 5 s for
273 24 scans. At least five spectra were collected for each sample, and they were manually corrected for
274 the baseline, and normalized for the intensity of the peak at 1000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the stretching
275 vibrational mode of aromatic rings (Sócrates, 2001), which do not vary their Raman intensity from
276 one sample to another, for the comparison between initial and ending time (days 0 and 16 were
277 considered). For the analysis of the reduction of the Raman signal at 1450 cm⁻¹ at each time point
278 (day 0, 3, 6, 9 and 16) at least 5 spectra were collected for each triplicate and both the average, and
279 the standard deviation were calculated. The spectra were corrected for the baseline and normalized

280 for the intensity of the signal at 1450 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the $\delta(\text{CH}_2/\text{CH}_3)$ of fatty acids, of the
281 starting point (day 0).

282 2.4.5 Statistical analysis

283 All the experiments were repeated three times on three different meat samples for each film and each
284 time point, and the reported data represents the mean values. The relative uncertainty budget
285 calculated as described in paragraph 2.2.5.3 has also been provided for each measurement. To
286 determine if there were significant differences between the results obtained, the Student t-test was
287 employed at a probability level of $p < 0.05$ or $p < 0.01$ (single or double star in the histograms,
288 respectively). The null hypothesis stated that the samples being analyzed were identical. However, if
289 the calculated t-value exceeded the tabulated values, the differences between the samples were
290 considered significant, and the null hypothesis was rejected. Furthermore, the calibration plot for
291 chemical analysis was adjusted using the least squares method.

292 3. Results and discussion

293 Extracts were obtained from grape marc and olive pomace of Spanish industries by: i) supercritical
294 fluid extraction (SFE) by CO_2 , which allows to separate mainly non-polar fractions which were not
295 expected to contain high amount of active molecules (this kind of extraction has been successfully
296 used to extract nonpolar fats from Parmesan grated cheese, without significant changes in sensory
297 tests (Yee et al., 2007)); ii) subsequent supercritical antisolvent extraction (SAE) of the solid residues
298 re-dissolved in ethanol, which should extract the highest amount of active agents; and iii) maceration
299 (MAC), as a more cost-effective procedure, in five solvents, which differ for polarity, and for two
300 time of incubation. Various fractions were collected at different step of the processes, characterized

301 and compared for their bactericidal properties and antioxidant power by both 2,2-diphenyl-1-
302 picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC) assays and comparing the
303 results with the content of active compounds obtained by Folin-Ciocalteu and ultra-performance
304 liquid chromatography-triple quadrupole-mass spectrometry (UPLC-TQ-MS). Furthermore,
305 *Moringa oleifera* leaves extracts were included in the study. Indeed, many works demonstrated that
306 this tropical plant possess valuable antioxidant, therapeutic and nutritional properties (Vergara-
307 Jimenez et al., 2017).

308 The extracts which showed the highest antioxidant properties were included in the biopolymer by
309 coating them on the film surface using a food-safe resin or in a double-layer system incorporating
310 them in the adhesive between two films of the polymer. Then, the two materials were characterized
311 for their radical scavenging capacity both in liquid by DPPH and in the atmosphere by the free radical
312 scavenging assay. The two systems which showed the highest efficacy in both the tests were used to
313 pack ground beef meat to test their protective action against lipid oxidation, in comparison to
314 conventional cellulose films. The analysis of meat was performed both indirectly by thiobarbituric
315 acid reactive substance (TBARS) and directly in situ by Raman microspectroscopy as a rapid and
316 non-destructive technique.

317 *3.1 Characterization of the antibacterial and antioxidant properties of the natural extracts*

318 In case of antibacterial properties, no significant antibacterial effects were observed for any of the
319 fraction tested (SI Figure S4) against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. In case of antioxidant properties, the
320 AP% was calculated for each one using the equation (2) and plotted against their concentration
321 (Figure 1).

322

323
324
325

Figure 1: DPPH assays results expressed as antioxidant power percentage (AP%).

326 AP% was plotted against sample concentrations for each extraction fractions by SFE (red lines), SAE (green
327 lines) and MAC for 10 days (solid lines) or 30 days (dashed lines) in the four different solvents (ethanol purple,
328 methanol pink, acetone carmine, DCM blue and water light blue lines) of A) grape marc extracts, B) moringa
329 leaves extracts and C) olive pomace extracts.

330 As expected, the fractions obtained by SFE and MAC in DCM showed the lowest values of AP%,
331 which, in most of the cases, do not even reach 50%. This is due to the mostly non-polar composition
332 of these extracts, which do not contain the active compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids and
333 tannins, usually extracted by polar solvents like water, ethanol or methanol. On the other hand, SAE
334 fractions showed very high antioxidant efficacy (green lines in the plot), especially those collected
335 immediately after the passage in the extractor (scheme in SI, Figure S1). Also, the macerates,
336 principally those obtained after 30 days with ethanol or methanol showed good capability to reduce
337 the DPPH radical, thanks to their higher polarity. The slope of the curves linearly reflects the
338 antioxidant efficacy of the samples, since the higher the slope, the lower sample concentration is
339 needed to reduce the same amount of DPPH. Consequently, it results clear that the highest efficacy
340 was obtained by grape marc extracts, excluding the SFE and MAC in DCM fractions, followed by
341 moringa and lastly by olive pomace extracts. This could be due to the more lipophilic composition of
342 olive extracts, which could partially affect their antioxidant efficacy in liquid assays with hydrophilic
343 conditions.

344 From these results, the half-maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) was interpolated for each sample,
345 excluding those that did not reach an AP% of 50%, analyzing a linear range of at least 4
346 concentrations in the surrounding of the 50% for each one (SI Table S2). The EC_{50} values were
347 compared with the ORAC assay, and the percentage of total content of polyphenols (w/w) determined
348 by the Folin-Ciocalteu assay (Table 1). A higher content of polyphenols is often related to a higher
349 antioxidant efficacy due to their capability to donate H^+ , thus reducing radical compounds. Indeed,
350 as expected, the samples with lower EC_{50} values displayed a higher content of polyphenols.

351 Furthermore, the SAE fractions presented the highest content of polyphenols, especially the two
352 collected from the first extractor. These samples were immediately followed by methanolic
353 macerates, solvent with the highest extractive capacity of active compounds. These findings are in
354 line with literature data (Babbar et al., 2014).

355 Additionally, grape marc extracts demonstrated the highest content of polyphenols with a relative
356 very high antioxidant activity in coherence with the fact that the peel and seeds of red grapes contain
357 huge amount of antioxidants (Lapornik et al., 2005).

358 For the maceration extracts the time of maceration seems to influence the extraction of active
359 compounds. Indeed, for both moringa and olive the best antioxidant efficacy and polyphenolic content
360 were obtained by the macerates for 30 days. Nevertheless, for grape the best results corresponded to
361 10 days of maceration. These findings were also confirmed by the redder color observed in the
362 macerates for 10 days in all the 4 solvents, while after 30 days the ethanolic ones showed a loss of
363 the red color indicating a lower content of phenolic compounds. This phenomenon is confirmed in
364 literature (S. Meyer et al., 1997) because excessive extraction times could cause oxidation of phenols
365 or their polymerization into insoluble species. Furthermore, it is known that the changes in the solid
366 to liquid ratio occurring over time could influence the mass transfer of active compounds.
367 Consequently, the optimal extraction conditions, including solvent, temperature and time of
368 extraction could be different between the plant materials due to their different compositions.

369 Even if the ORAC assay substantially confirmed the DPPH results, demonstrating that the SAE
370 fractions are more active in fluorescein protection from decay, it represents a more standard parameter
371 to quantify and compare the total antioxidant capacity (TAC) of these food derivatives representing
372 a unit of measurement for antioxidant content which was originally developed by the National

373 Institute on Aging (NIA) at the National Institutes of Health (NIH). This assay confirmed that among
374 the MAC, the moringa and olive extracted in methanol for 30 days, the grape extracted in acetone for
375 10 days retained the highest antioxidant efficacy showing high ORAC values. Furthermore, this
376 technique evidenced also a high extractive potential of water as regards grape marc, which confirm
377 that complementary techniques are needed to evaluate better the antioxidant capacity of each extract
378 when comparing different extractive methods and solvents.

379

Table 1. DPPH, ORAC and Folin Ciocalteu assays results for all the natural extracts.

Extract	Grape marc			Moringa			Olive pomace		
	EC ₅₀ (mg/l)	Total polyphenols % (w/w)	ORAC values (μmol TE/g)	EC ₅₀ (mg/l)	Total polyphenols % (w/w)	ORAC values (μmol TE/g)	EC ₅₀ (mg/l)	Total polyphenols % (w/w)	ORAC values (μmol TE/g)
SFE 1	1544 ± 148	9.9 ± 0.3	18730 ± 540	223 ± 87	2.931 ± 0.052	21790 ± 610	>5000	0.543 ± 0.062	2480 ± 130
SFE 2	2547 ± 508	8.4 ± 0.1	23960 ± 760	198 ± 53	2.83 ± 0.10	22990 ± 660	>5000	0.502 ± 0.058	3000 ± 80
SFE 3	4194 ± 1074	8.4 ± 0.1	19530 ± 570	115 ± 24	3.086 ± 0.057	24190 ± 670	>5000	0.689 ± 0.051	3340 ± 150
SFE 4	2985 ± 262	8.6 ± 0.2	31400 ± 860	738 ± 76	3.20 ± 0.08	22880 ± 640	>5000	0.577 ± 0.056	3530 ± 90
SAE 1	6.45 ± 0.91	45.0 ± 4.9	127700 ± 3700	69 ± 25	10.693 ± 0.067	x	46 ± 16	5.05 ± 0.11	4060 ± 110
SAE 2	6.0 ± 1.7	38.23 ± 0.74	91600 ± 2600	91 ± 17	10.217 ± 0.081	46900 ± 1400	66 ± 33	3.614 ± 0.081	2950 ± 140
SAE 3	352 ± 50	10.34 ± 0.12	80900 ± 2400	139 ± 35	3.479 ± 0.068	43500 ± 1300	139 ± 35	3.41 ± 0.15	3400 ± 180

MAC met 10d	6.7 ± 1.2	44.8 ± 1.9	74600 ± 2300	78 ± 13	7.476 ± 0.050	26040 ± 750	x	x	x
MAC ac 10d	3.80 ± 0.42	47.34 ± 0.71	78000 ± 2300	92 ± 20	4.69 ± 0.20	33900 ± 990	x	x	x
MAC et 10d	8.3 ± 1.9	31.78 ± 0.91	69000 ± 2000	93 ± 20	3.643 ± 0.029	42900 ± 1200	x	x	x
MAC DCM 10d	657 ± 12	9.70 ± 0.11	72300 ± 2000	149 ± 55	3.688 ± 0.082	30160 ± 890	x	x	x
MAC met 30d	31.0 ± 7.6	16.35 ± 0.12	75100 ± 2100	54 ± 10	7.60 ± 0.49	42600 ± 1200	46 ± 16	3.78 ± 0.15	4300 ± 110
MAC et 30d	29.8 ± 4.7	14.67 ± 0.21	60600 ± 1800	164 ± 30	5.652 ± 0.088	26240 ± 910	108 ± 34	3.309 ± 0.073	3420 ± 90
MAC ac 30d	51 ± 12	14.74 ± 0.59	75300 ± 2200	108 ± 20	4.085 ± 0.046	28300 ± 840	214 ± 71	2.133 ± 0.039	3340 ± 170
MAC DCM 30d	x	x	x	177 ± 71	3.968 ± 0.029	31670 ± 950	>5000	1.240 ± 0.031	3010 ± 170
MAC water 30d	21 ± 12	15.40 ± 0.21	89400 ± 3500	x	x	x	x	x	x

382

383

384 To better elucidate the relation between higher antioxidant properties and higher content of phenolic
385 compounds a semi-quantitative analysis of the content of the principal polyphenolic molecules was
386 performed by targeted UPLC-TQ-MS expressing the results as relative peak ratio% following
387 equation (1) (Figure 2 and Tables S3-S4-S5 SI).

388
389

390 **Figure 2: UPLC-TQ-MS results for each polyphenolic standard listed in the legend below the plots**
391 **obtained by each extract.**

392 A) grape marc, B) moringa leaves, and C) olive pomace samples.

393 The phenolic content of all the three plant extracts is mostly composed of GA, more abundant in the
394 samples with high polyphenolic content according to the Folin-Ciocalteu assay, such as the MAC and
395 the SAE fractions. In particular, grape extracts (except for the moringa MAC in methanol for 30 days,
396 with the highest amount of GA) confirmed their highest content of polyphenolic compounds including
397 catechin, epicatechin and epicatechin gallate. However, the moringa extracts showed the presence of
398 caffeine especially in the MAC in methanol and in the first SAE fraction. Even if the olive pomace
399 extracts contained lower amount of polyphenols, they evidenced the presence of quite high amount
400 of epigallocatechin and epigallocatechin gallate, especially in the first two SAE fractions and in the
401 MAC in ethanol and methanol, which suggest a potentiality of antioxidant effects also for these
402 extracts. These results are perfectly in line with the DPPH, ORAC and Folin-Ciocalteu ones,
403 confirming that the grape extracts are those with the highest content of active polyphenols, antioxidant
404 effects and content of GA. For all the three plants, the more efficient solvent to extract is methanol.

405 *3.2 Active films production and antioxidant efficacy characterization*

406 According to the obtained results, the extracts of grape MAC in acetone and in methanol for 10 days,
407 moringa MAC in methanol for 10 days and 30 days, and olive pomace MAC in methanol and ethanol
408 for 30 days were selected to be incorporated in a biodegradable polymer. They were coated on a film
409 of cellulose-based biopolymer or put in an adhesive between two layers of the same material. The
410 criterion was based on their solubility in the varnish for the coating or in the food-safe adhesive. In
411 both cases, the concentration of extract was 5% w/w. MAC was chosen instead of SAE as more
412 sustainable and cheaper extraction processes (Vongsak et al., 2013).

413 The AP% was calculated accordingly as shown in Table 2. DPPH assay evidenced that the two most
414 effective DPPH radical scavengers, apart from the two standards, GA and Trolox, were the film

415 coated with 5% of the moringa MAC in methanol for 30 days, and the grape MAC in acetone for 10
416 days. AP% of $(50.1 \pm 7.8)\%$ and $(48 \pm 11)\%$, respectively, were obtained, thus suggesting a very
417 promising antioxidant efficacy.

418 The results of ability to scavenge $\text{OH}\cdot$ radicals by developed active films are also presented in Table
419 2.

420
421

Table 2: DPPH and free OH· radical scavenging assays of the active films results.

Sample	Antioxidant Power %	Mean H% *
Blank (varnish)	0.1 ± 5.9	100
Gallic acid	89.8 ± 3.0	60.53 ± 0.16
Moringa MAC methanol 10d	37.4 ± 4.9	57.92 ± 0.10
Moringa MAC methanol 30d	50.1 ± 7.8	52.13 ± 0.17
Olives MAC ethanol 30d	13.3 ± 2.4	74.01 ± 0.32
Olives MAC methanol 30d	13.0 ± 2.9	55.11 ± 0.19
Blank (adhesive)	5.7 ± 7.0	100
Trolox	71.6 ± 6.7	65.81 ± 0.13
Grape MAC acetone 10d	48 ± 11	58.10 ± 0.18
Grape MAC methanol 10d	28.6 ± 6.7	66.84 ± 0.10

422
423

*Calculated by equation (3)

424 The best radical scavenging capacity was obtained by the film coated with 5% of the moringa MAC
425 in methanol for 30 days with H% of 52.13 ± 0.17 , which is even lower than that of GA. This test
426 evidenced a good radical scavenging capacity also of the films coated with olive MAC, which did not
427 show satisfactory results in the DPPH assay.

428 This could be due to the different lipophilic content between the extracts: olive pomace extracts may
429 contain more lipidic fractions deriving from the oils of the seeds which cannot be dissolved in the
430 methanolic DPPH solution resulting in a reduction of the total antioxidant efficacy. However, this
431 assay highlighted the ability of these films to scavenge atmospheric free radicals suggesting that
432 maybe a more volatile part of these extracts could have some potential as non-contact materials active
433 on the atmosphere around food.

434 Furthermore, also the Trolox and grape extracts showed a good OH· radical scavenging capacity,
435 comparable to that of GA and moringa, even in the case of adhesive, where their availability could
436 be mitigated by the presence of the layer of cellulose-based biopolymer. In consequence, different
437 tests are needed for a correct characterization of all the antioxidant effects of the produced active
438 materials. Some of them are more indicated for the direct contact use, others for non-contact
439 packaging due to their higher scavenging activity, or due to their behavior against lipophilic
440 substances.

441 Finally, the two most active films of all those tested (moringa MAC Met 30d and grape MAC Ac
442 10d) were chosen to be applied on a real food matrix. The two different packaging systems, direct
443 contact (coating) and indirect non-contact radicals scavenging activity (double layer + adhesive) were
444 considered.

445 For these films thickness, transmission rates of oxygen (OTR) and water vapour (WVTR), as well as
446 permeability properties were studied. Data are summarized in SI (Table S6). Two independent films
447 and ten determinations per film were considered in all the cases.

448 *3.3 Active films application for protection of ground beef meat from oxidative damage*

449 Since lipid peroxidation is one of the main causes of the degradation of meat, during transportation
450 or storage, meat oxidation over 16 days of storage in the fridge at 4 °C was compared with the same
451 meat packed in the blanks (cellulose polymer with only varnish or adhesive without adding any active
452 agent) and in the films with 5% of the two standards (GA and Trolox) as negative and positive controls
453 respectively (Figure 3 A-D).

454

Figure 3: Ground beef meat packaging preparation and TBARS results.

A) Weighting and flattening of meat samples. B) Packing of meat in rectangles of the active packaging. C) Thermosealing of the PET bags outside the test sample leaving the same area of non-modified atmosphere inside. D) Final sample to be stored in the fridge. E-F) TBARS assay results of meat samples packed in blank (blue bars), in film coated with 5% of GA (carmine bars) or moringa MAC Met 30d (green bars) and in film with 5% of Trolox (red bars) or grape MAC Ac 10d (purple bars) in the adhesive between two cellulose layers. Asterisks: *: p-value < 0.05. **: p-value < 0.01.

465 The TBARS results are represented in Figure 3E and 3F and Table S7 (SI). The more MDA/kg is
466 measured the more peroxidation of lipids took place on the analyzed piece of meat.

467 The relatively high uncertainty values among the three replicates could be caused by the differences
468 in total content of lipids among the samples. These results evidenced significant differences of lipids
469 oxidation between the active and blank samples. Considering the moringa and grape films, a
470 statistically significant protection is already visible from day 9 ($p < 0.05$ for moringa and $p < 0.01$ for
471 grape). The results of the two controls showed the rightness of the test development. Meat packed in
472 the blanks showed oxidation rising over time, whereas the samples packed in GA and Trolox kept the
473 meat integrity over all the time of storage tested. Significant differences compared to the blanks ($p <$
474 0.05) were noticed after only 6 days. After 16 days, lipid oxidation of blanks reached about 84%,
475 whereas the corresponding to samples of moringa and grape active packaging was only 24% and
476 34%, respectively. Furthermore, those stored in the packaging with GA and Trolox reported 7% and
477 26%, respectively. The percentages of oxidation were calculated using the following equation:

$$478 \text{ OX\%} = [(A_{d0} - A_{d16}) / A_{d0}] \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

479 Where A_{d0} and A_{d16} are the absorbance of the sample measured at days 0 and 16, respectively.

480 Therefore, the minced beef meat packed in the cellulose biopolymer with 5% the moringa MAC Met
481 30d and that in the 5% grape MAC Ac 10d demonstrated to be able to protect ground beef meat lipid
482 peroxidation by at least 60% and 50%, respectively, after 16 days of storage in the fridge.

483 *3.4 Raman spectroscopy as a non-destructive and rapid alternative to TBARS assay*

484 To confirm the observed protective action of these films against lipid oxidation of the meat the
485 analysis of the hamburgers was performed also by Raman microspectroscopy as a more direct
486 measurement method.

487 In particular, Raman spectroscopy was already reported to follow the lipid oxidation of meat over
488 time (Moudache et al., 2017; Olsen et al., 2007) but these studies eventually involved a step of lipid
489 extraction or the use of special sample holder with silver nanoparticles employing the surface-
490 enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) configuration in order to evidence the Raman signals.
491 However, in this work meat was analyzed directly by non-enhanced Raman spectroscopy without
492 using any preparative steps or extractions.
493 The Raman spectra of minced beef meat were collected at each time point for all the samples before
494 the TBARS assay.
495 A complete average Raman spectrum of meat can be found in the SI (Figure S5). All the spectra were
496 pre-processed for baseline correction to eliminate fluorescence contribution and normalized by the
497 intensity of the signal at 1000 cm^{-1} corresponding to aromatic rings stretching modes (Sócrates, 2001),
498 which do not vary their Raman intensity from one sample to another. The average ($n \geq 5$) of the
499 normalized intensity of the peak at 1450 cm^{-1} , due to $\delta(\text{CH}_2/\text{CH}_3)$ of fatty acids, was plotted over
500 time (Figure 4).
501

502

503

504

Figure 4: Raman *in situ* analysis of minced meat oxidation over time.

505

A-B) Reduction of the intensity of the typical Raman peak assigned to lipids (δCH_2) at 1450 cm⁻¹ during meat

506

oxidation for 0 (dashed lines) and 16 (solid lines) days are shown.

507

Measured Raman intensities of the peak at 1450 cm⁻¹ of meat over time. The sample in triplicate corresponds to meat packed in cellulose

508

biopolymer with 5% of moringa MAC Met 30d (green line), or grape MAC Ac 10d (purple line), or GA

509

(carmine line), or Trolox (red line) or varnish or adhesive without any active agent as blanks (blue lines).

510

511 The Raman analysis of meat revealed that the intensity of the band at 1450 cm⁻¹ significantly
512 decreases over time in the blank samples, indicating a progressive unsaturation of the fatty acids
513 (Moudache et al., 2017). This decrease was significantly lower in the sample packed in the cellulose
514 with 5% of both moringa and grape extracts and even less in the sample with GA or Trolox. These
515 results agree with those obtained by the TBARS assay and confirm the protective action of the active
516 films tested against meat oxidation.

517 Furthermore, this demonstrated, for the first time to the authors' knowledge, that non-enhanced
518 Raman microspectroscopy, if applied in these conditions of acquisition, is sensitive enough to follow
519 the peroxidation of lipids of meat directly *in situ* without the needing of any sample preparation,
520 specific supports or particularly trained users. Thus, in respect to TBARS or other analytical assays
521 the time of analysis are reduced to few minutes and the samples remain intact. This could be very
522 interesting in the optic of translating this kind of food oxidation analysis in an industrial scale greatly
523 reducing the costs of analysis.

524 **4. Conclusions**

525 Many extracts, obtained by different procedures from *Moringa oleifera* Lam. desiccated leaves, olive
526 oil and red wine industrial waste, were characterized for their composition and antioxidant efficacy.
527 It was evinced that those obtained by SAE and MAC revealed to have the highest antioxidant efficacy,
528 by both DPPH and ORAC assays, due to their highest content of polyphenolic compounds and other
529 active molecules, especially GA. Among all macerates, methanol provided the highest extraction
530 yield of active compounds, followed by ethanol and acetone thanks to their higher polarity and

531 affinity for phenolic molecules. As for grape marc, water also resulted to extract fractions with high
532 antioxidant efficacy.

533 In particular, the importance of comparing the results obtained by different assays was emphasized
534 here, since different properties of the natural extracts were considered, obtaining a more global
535 evaluation of their antioxidant activity.

536 Two kinds of cellulose-based biopolymer packaging were developed containing 5% of the highest
537 antioxidant macerates of moringa and grape extracts, one obtained by coating and one mixing the
538 agent in the adhesive between two films. Both demonstrated a high radical scavenging ability in
539 different *in vitro* assays as well as when applied on real food matrices. Specifically, both packaging
540 systems demonstrated to protect ground beef meat from lipid peroxidation by at least 50% over 16
541 days. This protective action was confirmed by direct *in situ* Raman spectroscopy, avoiding any
542 extractive step and strengthening the reliability of the results.

543 Hence, even if other analyses should be due on these materials before ensuring their possible
544 commercialization, such as permeability and migration test, this work could be considered valuable
545 in the field of food packaging, proposing the use of sustainable and degradable materials together
546 with an innovative way to recover food industry waste to prolong the food shelf-life.

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554 **References**

- 555 Adedapo, A. A., Jimoh, F. O., Koduru, S., Afolayan, A. J., & Masika, P. J. (2008). Antibacterial and
556 antioxidant properties of the methanol extracts of the leaves and stems of *Calpurnia aurea*. *BMC*
557 *Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-8-53>
- 558 Ahn, D. U., Olson, D. G., Jo, C., Chen, X., Wu, C., & Lee, J. I. (1998). Effect of muscle type,
559 packaging, and irradiation on lipid oxidation, volatile production, and color in raw pork patties.
560 *Meat Science*, 49(1), 27–39. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0309-1740\(97\)00101-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0309-1740(97)00101-0)
- 561 Babbar, N., Oberoi, H. S., Sandhu, S. K., & Bhargav, V. K. (2014). Influence of different solvents in
562 extraction of phenolic compounds from vegetable residues and their evaluation as natural
563 sources of antioxidants. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 51(10), 2568–2575.
564 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-012-0754-4>
- 565 Barbosa-Pereira, L., Aurrekoetxea, G. P., Angulo, I., Paseiro-Losada, P., & Cruz, J. M. (2014).
566 Development of new active packaging films coated with natural phenolic compounds to improve
567 the oxidative stability of beef. *Meat Science*, 97(2), 249–254.
568 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2014.02.006>
- 569 Benbettaieb, N., Tanner, C., Cayot, P., Karbowiak, T., & Debeaufort, F. (2018). Impact of functional
570 properties and release kinetics on antioxidant activity of biopolymer active films and coatings.
571 *Food Chemistry*, 242, 369–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.09.065>

- 572 Busolo, M. A., & Lagaron, J. M. (2015). Antioxidant polyethylene films based on a resveratrol
573 containing Clay of Interest in Food Packaging Applications. *Food Packaging and Shelf Life*, 6,
574 30–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fpsl.2015.08.004>
- 575 Henriott, M. L., Herrera, N. J., Ribeiro, F. A., Hart, K. B., Bland, N. A., Eskridge, K., & Calkins, C.
576 R. (2020). Impact of myoglobin oxygenation state prior to frozen storage on color stability of
577 thawed beef steaks through retail display. *Meat Science*, 170.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2020.108232>
- 579 Karak, N. (2012). *Vegetable oil-based polymers: Properties, processing and applications*.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857097149>
- 581 Krzyzanowska, J., Janda, B., Pecio, L., Stochmal, A., Oleszek, W., Czubačka, A., Przybys, M., &
582 Doroszevska, T. (2011). *Determination of Polyphenols in Mentha longifolia and M. piperita*
583 *Field-Grown and In Vitro Plant Samples Using UPLC-TQ-MS*.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaoac/94.1.43>
- 585 Kupina, S., Fields, C., Roman, M. C., & Brunelle, S. L. (2018). Determination of total phenolic
586 content using the Folin-C assay: Single-laboratory validation, first action 2017.13. *Journal of*
587 *AOAC International*, 101(5), 1466–1472. <https://doi.org/10.5740/jaoacint.18-0031>
- 588 Lafka, T. I., Sinanoglou, V., & Lazos, E. S. (2007). On the extraction and antioxidant activity of
589 phenolic compounds from winery wastes. *Food Chemistry*, 104(3), 1206–1214.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2007.01.068>
- 591 Lapornik, B., Prošek, M., & Wondra, A. G. (2005). Comparison of extracts prepared from plant by-
592 products using different solvents and extraction time. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 71(2), 214–
593 222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2004.10.036>

594 Marsh, K., & Bugusu, B. (2007). Food packaging - Roles, materials, and environmental issues:
595 Scientific status summary. In *Journal of Food Science* (Vol. 72, Issue 3).
596 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2007.00301.x>

597 Moudache, M., Colon, M., Nerín, C., & Zaidi, F. (2016). Phenolic content and antioxidant activity of
598 olive by-products and antioxidant film containing olive leaf extract. *Food Chemistry*, 212, 521–
599 527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.06.001>

600 Moudache, M., Nerín, C., Colon, M., & Zaidi, F. (2017). Antioxidant effect of an innovative active
601 plastic film containing olive leaves extract on fresh pork meat and its evaluation by Raman
602 spectroscopy. *Food Chemistry*, 229, 98–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.02.023>

603 Nerín, C. (2010). Antioxidant active food packaging and antioxidant edible films. In *Oxidation in*
604 *Foods and Beverages and Antioxidant Applications* (pp. 496–515).
605 <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857090331.3.496>

606 Nerín, C., Tovar, L., Djenane, D., Camo, J., Salafranca, J., Beltrán, J. A., & Roncalés, P. (2006).
607 Stabilization of beef meat by a new active packaging containing natural antioxidants. *Journal of*
608 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54(20), 7840–7846. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf060775c>

609 Nerín, C., Tovar, L., & Salafranca, J. (2008). Behaviour of a new antioxidant active film versus
610 oxidizable model compounds. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 84(2), 313–320.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2007.05.027>

612 Ning, Z. W., Zhai, L. X., Peng, J., Zhao, L., Huang, T., Lin, C. Y., Chen, W. H., Luo, Z., Xiao, H. T.,
613 & Bian, Z. X. (2019). Simultaneous UPLC-TQ-MS/MS determination of six active components
614 in rat plasma: Application in the pharmacokinetic study of Cyclocarya paliurus leaves. *Chinese*
615 *Medicine (United Kingdom)*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13020-019-0248-7>

- 616 Ou, B., Chang, T., Huang, D., & Prior, R. L. (2013). Determination of total antioxidant capacity by
617 oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC) using fluorescein as the fluorescence probe: First
618 action 2012.23. *Journal of AOAC International*, 96(6), 1372–1376.
619 <https://doi.org/10.5740/jaoacint.13-175>
- 620 Oyedemi, S. O., Bradley, G., & Afolayan, A. J. (2012). In vitro and in vivo antioxidant properties of
621 aqueous extract from *Strychnos henningsii* Gilg stem bark. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*.
622 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2012.08.237>
- 623 Pezo, D., Salafranca, J., & Nerín, C. (2006). Design of a method for generation of gas-phase hydroxyl
624 radicals, and use of HPLC with fluorescence detection to assess the antioxidant capacity of
625 natural essential oils. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 385(7), 1241–1246.
626 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-006-0395-4>
- 627 Prieto, J. M. (2012). Dr Prieto's DPPH Microplate Protocol Procedure: Preparation of DPPH Radical,
628 and antioxidant scavenging assay. In *Dr Prieto's DPPH Microplate Protocol* (pp. 7–9).
- 629 Realini, C. E., & Marcos, B. (2014). Active and intelligent packaging systems for a modern society.
630 *Meat Science*, 98(3), 404–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2014.06.031>
- 631 Rhim, J. W., Park, H. M., & Ha, C. S. (2013). Bio-nanocomposites for food packaging applications.
632 In *Progress in Polymer Science* (Vol. 38, Issues 10–11, pp. 1629–1652).
633 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.05.008>
- 634 Ribeiro, F. A., Lau, S. K., Furbeck, R. A., Herrera, N. J., Henriott, M. L., Bland, N. A., Fernando, S.
635 C., Subbiah, J., Sullivan, G. A., & Calkins, C. R. (2021). Ultimate pH effects on dry-aged beef
636 quality. *Meat Science*, 172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2020.108365>

637 Rodis, P. S., Karathanos, V. T., & Mantzavinou, A. (2002). Partitioning of olive oil antioxidants
638 between oil and water phases. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 50(3), 596–601.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf010864j>

640 S. Meyer, A., Yi, O.-S., A. Pearson, D., L. Waterhouse, A., & N. Frankel, E. (1997). Inhibition of
641 Human Low-Density Lipoprotein Oxidation in Relation to Composition of Phenolic
642 Antioxidants in Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*). *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 45(5),
643 1638–1643. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf960721a>

644 Sócrates, G. (2001). Infrared and Raman Characteristic Group Frequencies. Tables and charts. In
645 *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy*.

646 Vongsak, B., Sithisarn, P., Mangmool, S., Thongpraditchote, S., Wongkrajang, Y., & Gritsanapan,
647 W. (2013). Maximizing total phenolics, total flavonoids contents and antioxidant activity of
648 *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract by the appropriate extraction method. *Industrial Crops and*
649 *Products*, 44, 566–571. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2012.09.021>

650